
ARRIVAL OF DIGITAL CULTURE IN LIBRARIES: SUSTAINABILITY OF LEARNING RESOURCES

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Abstract:

The present article highlight on various views regarding the changing nature of learning counterpart of traditional to modern technology based. Author has expressed his views with keeping objective as changing role of libraries in digital culture and sustainability of resources. Library is important component of education system and it plays vital role in learning counterpart. Today, it works in digital environment for providing the e-resources via online access mode. This growth and development is moving towards the sustainable development and availability of learning resources to long-life basis. It also assists somewhat towards Sustainable Development Goals of 2030. In this way, present article insight various view in current global environment.

Keywords: *Digital culture, learning center, SDG Goals, Information and Communication Technology.*

Introduction:

In primitive period, the sources of any type of information or knowledge were in different form with strict bounded rules and regulations. Religious places, Madarsas, temples were playing role in preserving and disseminating sources of information and knowledge. At that time, orally and mouth to mouth systems were popular for getting any information. But gradually, this situation has been changed due to various factors like birth of printing technology and so on. Nalanda, Takshashila, Vallabhi etc. learning centers were more popular in the world. India having great history of education in primitive era and proved through great learner as Mathematician Varahmihir, Kautilya and so on eminent personalities have been produced from this Indian

educational culture. We all are well known about Nalanda Universities library resources collection and it indicate that India was rich in knowledge domain among the world. Today, these ideal memories are stimulating in this digital culture and India is going towards for achievement the previous status in present scenario.

Teaching and learning both wheels are important to run towards the excellence education. Libraries are nothing but the part of learning component of education system. The traditional based resources still are present in every type of library. Due to the technological revolution, the nature and feature of traditional based learning resources have been changed and arrival in electronic form. If we look at this changing nature of

resources, it is a really become boon to learner community for acquiring the unlimited knowledge for fulfillment of the learners academic thrust. Although, there is some demerits of such resources but as compare to profit and benefit with knowledge view, it has more merits and hence these resources are playing important role in embedding sustainable learning sources. It is need of the hour of every reader to get any type of resources within time and it is possible only in this digital culture of learning center.

Objective of the Study:

Objectives of the study are as per following.

1. To discuss about changing role of libraries in the digital age.
2. To highlight on sustainability of resources and meeting with SDG goals.

What is sustainable?

In Cambridge dictionary the meaning of sustainable is mentioned as, “causing or made in a way that causes, little or no damage to the environment and therefore able to continue for a long time”. This sustainable concept is very broad and it touch to various aspect such as sustainable development, sustainable growth of each part like economic, social, cultural, education and so on. In 2015 the [United Nations General Assembly](#) adopted the [Sustainable Development Goals](#) (SDGs) (2015 to 2030) and explained how the goals are integrated and indivisible to achieve sustainable development at the global level(Wikipedia accessed on 2ndsept. 2022). At present, New Education Policy is arrival and entire structure of education has been modified and some sustainable goal has been set which are relevant to

today’s global scenario. To survive in the coming year to every human being, there are many opportunities as well as challenges and hence education should be coup up these 21st centuries need and such way our education systems is going towards it. Libraries are considered as knowledge resource center which are playing significant role for fulfillment of aims and objectives of education system. In this regard, Information and Communication Technology have given many opportunities for growth and development of academic community as well as sustainable preservation of knowledge.

Libraries in the Digital Era:

Library is a core part of any type of education system. It holds the different type of resources according the needs of the user community. Resources make available in different form like books, journals, thesis, report, newspapers, and reference material and so on. All these resources now changed in the form of electronic and libraries have been moved towards this culture. Still Indian culture, fully electronic based library concept not increased except few of them such as National Digital Library of India etc. Blended or hybrid library system has been flourished in more number. Many study shown that majority libraries are moving towards the electronic environment with keeping traditional based resources.

Digital Technology and Sustainable Development:

Technology has given us various opportunities for fulfillment the aims and objectives of education system. It has a strong power to change the traditional form into modern way within a few periods. Recently, every human being has

been taken experience of Covid Pandemic situation with various aspects. It has taught us various things including the value and importance of ICT enabled resources.

All over the world, education has been started to change the traditional mode of teaching and learning and moved towards ICT platform. Learning resources have been flourished lot in digital forms such as audio; video based teaching learning resources, Power point presentations, electronic books, e-journals and e-newspapers. Whatever needs to learn is making available in the digital form. It means that traditional based resources have taken place in digital mode. Apart from it, Not only digital resources are making available but also transitional ways or disseminating path also increased like what Aapp, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, email and so many social networking sites have been playing important role to spread the knowledge of piece and information component within a fraction of second. It's a magic of recent developed technology. Information and Communication Technology has given us a golden opportunity to survive the valuable knowledge with perpetual and sustainable way. There is no fear about vanish and damage or injury to content of the knowledge. Therefore, in future, it will be permanent sustainable development in knowledge resources domain.

Digital Technology assists to SDG Goal 2030:

Seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aimed to build a more prosperous, more equal, and more secure world by the year 2030 have been developed. They have been adopted by 193 Member States at the UN General Assembly Summit in September 2015 as a part of their agenda for Sustainable

Development. India is a signatory to this summit and is strongly committed to the 2030 agenda.(M. Prabhakar-2015). Our Indian Education System is going towards this path with global vision and mission. Out of 30 goals, 3 are purely related to education system and close to learning counterpart. Library is considered with various names such as Knowledge Resource Center, Learning Center and so on. Goal Number fourth is that ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities to all. This goal clearly indicates that learning facilities should be available to each and every person without any discrimination. Library is nothing but treasure of knowledge house. Today, it has changed its traditional shape into digital form and providing valuable resources via online platform.

Online access facility contains various features such as anytime, anywhere access, equality is possible through this mode, it assist to environment preservation by digitizing content etc. It means that education component is able to assist for fulfillment of some SDG goals through library environment. Goal number 15 & 16 are also associated in some quantity with learning counterpart and in this regard also library can play a vital role to aid in SDG goals, vision and mission.

Conclusion:

Education is important component for growth and development of human being. It has changed its traditional shape into digital environment. In this regard, Information and Communication Technology have been played vital role to change the traditional culture of education into global need environment. Library is an important component of any type of education system and it has also reshaped

to itself by applying the digital technology. Many study indicated that libraries are moving towards the digital culture. It means that content of knowledge and information is being provided in e-forms. By considering the benefits of electronic resources most of the libraries are going to make available different type of access facility to their users. It is urgent need of the time to extend such access facility for survive in global competitive environment as well as to overcome the natural pandemic situation like Corona. At present, library are playing role as learning center keeping view of Indian Education System as well as SDG Goals.

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Abstract:

Libraries and Information Centres (LICs) are expected to offer library services with modern devices, create library and information products conducive to cater to the changing needs of students and offer both the library services and products in a way that will save their time in retrieval of relevant information and at the same time they will get access to all the resources available on one single platform. In this context, Web Scale Discovery services and its significance as a new platform for effective access to e-resources is explained in this article.

Key Words: *web scale discovery service, discovery service, index based discovery, E-resources, direct access to e-resources, library service.*
